

IMPACTS OF FACEBOOK ON UNDERGRADUATE COLLEGE STUDENTS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Kunwar Mahendra Pratap Singh*
Dr. Madhu Tyagi**

Abstract: One of the most popular social networking platforms among students is Facebook. Undergraduate students who spend most of their time on Facebook are impacted and affected by these platforms. Other people are likely to affect students who use Facebook regularly. Their studies, on the other hand, are likely to be disrupted. Instead of revising their schoolwork, students are enticed to spend a significant amount of time of Facebook. This study looked into why undergraduate college students use Facebook and what they had to say about it. In order to evaluate and analyze the data, this study used a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods. The respondents were undergraduate college students from Babu Shivnath Agrawal College, Mathura that is affiliated to Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Agra. According to the findings, frequent usage of social media such as Facebook can have a negative impact on student's academic performance. However, Book has the potential to improve student's academic achievement. Facebook serves as a communication platform, allowing users to share information and learn from one another. Facebook helps them with their studies. College students can now brainstorm and collaborate in the Group Chat on Facebook to share and trade information. As a result, learners and lecturers will benefit from the use of Facebook in learning as a tool in education during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Keywords: Facebook, Undergraduate students, Academic Performance, Instructional Tool

Introduction: Individuals can use social networking sites such as Instagram, Twitter, WhatsApp, Facebook to exhibit themselves, articulate their social networks and form or

*Assistant Professor, Deptt. Of Sociology, P.P. N. (PG) College, Kanpur (Affiliated to CSJM University, Kanpur)

****Professor, Deptt. Of Sociology, BSA College, Mathura (Affiliated to Dr.B.R.Ambedkar University Agra)**

maintain connections with others. Users can utilize the sites to meet new individuals or communicate with people they already know offline. Facebook, the online social networking site discussed in this article, allow users to create an online profile, collect “friends” who can write comments on each other’s profiles. Member of Facebook can also create virtual groups based on shared interests, check what classes they share, and learn about each other’s hobbies, musical tastes, interests and relationship status by looking at their profiles. Facebook was created in 2004 by Mark Zuckerberg with his some friends. Recently Facebook has 2.9 billion monthly active users and if we talk specifically about India, there are 416.6 million monthly active users (worldpopulationreview.com, 2022). This data demonstrate its impact on society and its reach among youth. Facebook’s value grew during the pandemic because it enabled people to connect and helped society communicate. During the pandemic, Facebook played a critical role. Facebook had piqued the interest of researchers who wanted to learn more about its various characteristics and how they effect society. The majority of existing academic study on Facebook has concentrated on issues of identity presentation and privacy(Gross& Acquisti,2005; Stutzman,2006). The majority of studies have focused on the negative effect of Facebook, however this study focuses on the interaction between students and their peers throughout the pandemic.

During this pandemic, the use of Facebook in learning has been practiced. This can be utilized for discussion and sharing of resources such as reading materials, presentations and other instructional material supplied via Facebook Page, messages by the teacher. Since then, Facebook has grown in popularity and is now used by people all over the world. Because of the different platforms that Facebook provides such as obtaining information, talking with loved ones, running and advertising a business for amusement purpose, and many more, using Facebook has become one of the habits that each individual has been addicted to. Due to this phenomena Facebook has shown to be useful because it is simple and user-friendly, and it can also be used for education, particularly during this pandemic.

The students who recently entered college, particularly those who do not have sufficient resources, are using Facebook to learn new things. Because of its user-friendly atmosphere, first year college students priorities the use of Facebook. It also includes useful tools such as Facebook Groups and Messenger, which allow students to construct a virtual classroom and use it as a useful tool for their academic needs. Students from various college use Facebook to communicate in a variety of ways, including chatting, videos conferencing, posting images and videos, sharing and exchanging information and more. As a result, children develop a fondness for Facebook, which has now become an integral part of their everyday lives.

First year college students use Facebook for a variety of reasons, including enjoyment, college activities and many others that can have an impact on their academic

performance. College students' use of Facebook might have a favorable or negative impact on their academic achievement.

Ellison et al (2011) in their study claims, when it comes to assignments, projects and other schoolwork, students chose to use Facebook or other social networking sites. It will have a negative impact on their academic achievement since they will be enticed to log on to Facebook instead of doing their schoolwork. Instead of looking for information about their classes, they spend a lot of time on the platform being entertained.

Boholano et al (2021) cited a few exercises towards making strides the quality of instruction within the Philippines with the conviction that well-equipped instructors can provide great quality educating and subsequently creating all inclusive competitive learners. Besides understudies there are uncovered to utilizing Facebook to communicate, socialize and for instructive purposes. In school, for illustration, understudies are utilizing Facebook particularly when they ought to communicate with their mentor and with their classmates to inquire for particular data and other occurrences. In line with this, understudies are too affectionate of utilizing Facebook to associated with companies and amusement.

A few analyst have coined the term “friend sickness” to allude to the trouble caused by the misfortune of association to old companions when a youthful individual moves absent to college (Paul & Brier,2001). Web advances include conspicuously in a think about of communication innovation utilize by this populace by Cummings, Lee and Kraut (2006), who found that administrations like mail and moment informing offer assistance college understudies stay near to their college companions after they take off domestic for college. We subsequently present a degree centering particularly on the support of existing social capital after this major life alter experienced by college understudies, centering on their capacity to use and keep up social associations from college.

Furthermore, as stated in the previous study, “in light of this epidemic where social separation is required and mass gathering is outlawed, educational institutions are obligated to develop ways to further capacitate teachers”. Facebook is necessary for giving assignments and discussions via Facebook Messenger or the Facebook Page. Teachers and students are utilizing technology to its best potential in order to meet the objectives of the lesson.

Several research on the use of Facebook in teaching and learning have been undertaken. This study investigates why students use Facebook and what their experiences and feedback have been on various social networking sites. The researchers discovered that in colleges and universities, teachers and mentors use Facebook to make announcements, keep students up to date on school activities, and send and upload educational files, all of which are beneficial to college students' learning. College students, nowadays, have reason have reason to log in their Facebook accounts on a regular basis. As a result, college students have become addicted to Facebook and reliant on the services it provides. The purpose of this study was to see how important it is for new college students to use Facebook in their teaching and learning. Furthermore, the experience and feedback of students using Facebook as an instructional tool will be investigated.

Methods: The result of the data acquired were determined using both qualitative and quantitative research methods in this study. The qualitative research strategy quantifies the issues by generating numerical data or data that may be converted into meaningful statistics. Attitude, views and conduct are all quantified using this method. The quantitative data collection in this study comprises paper surveys of college students at public colleges concerning their use of Facebook.

Only random college students in Babu Shivnath Agrawal College, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India were given survey questionnaire. They must respond to ten questions on a questionnaire. Each choice in the questionnaire is represented by a box. Respondents are asked to check the boxes the best describe their Facebook usage and behaviors. In the second component, which is qualitative, the participants were given a table with ten scenarios and asked to check the column that corresponded to how frequently they use Facebook. They can also leave feedback on the offered space. Participants in the study were issued Google Forms. Only college students aged 18 to 21 years old from BSA College, Mathura, are eligible to participate in the study. Ethical issues are observed, such as sending an informed consent and in the case of a specific respondents rejection, the researchers are not in the authority to impose such declination, but rather to take into account the participant’s decisions. This study carries no risk because all documents were distributed over Facebook Messenger to follow the required health routine in the wake of the Covid-19 pandemic. This research is entirely academic. The responses and details of the respondents were kept in strict confidence.

Results and Discussion:

The researcher tabulated, evaluated and interpreted the data based on the information acquired. For better understanding and presentation all refined data is being presented by pie chart:

The biggest reason students used Facebook is for social interaction (36.5%). This implies that students use Facebook to make new friends and expand their social circles. Additionally, students utilize Facebook to maintain continual contact with their loved ones. They socialized on Facebook by communicating openly with one another and freely expressing themselves. Facebook has become the most popular social media platform among

college students because it allows them to express themselves with their peers, with social interaction accounting for the biggest percentage of other reasons for using Facebook. “Facebook is the leading site for college students”. Taylor, Mulligan and Ishida (2012) had mentioned this in their research. This is accurate in this study because the majority of students and teachers use Facebook to communicate about school events and other educational responsibilities. Facebook is especially important in the educational side of students’ lives (24.5%). Students can effortlessly send and receive documents or files for their studies using this program.

Furthermore, when students are bored, they turn to social media as a way to at least enjoy their free time (21%). Several students now use Facebook at their leisure, making it the cheapest way to watch movies, videos, news, listen to music, and other forms of media. Facebook also has a diverse selection of games that students like playing. “ Facebook seems well-suited to enhance the students’ experiences, given that through profiles highlights both commonalities and distinctions among participants”, says Ellison, Steinfield and Lampe (2007). Users can, for example, play games with people from all over the world, watch movies and listen to music. Above all, it facilitates the formation on new relationships among users on this site. These findings back up Cuesta et al (2016)’s study, which found that “Using social media in students and instructors dialogues (e.g. Chats , videos call) in a closed Facebook forum overseen by the teacher, sought to promote students integration into academic culture and implementation”. Students utilize Facebook via publishing, sharing and reacting to content, according to the research. According to Nadkarni and Hoofman (2012), “ students utilize Facebook for self-presentation”. It could be through the use of photographs to garner more likes or other responses. “It is increasingly vital to evaluate the consequences of online learning practices”. Wise, Skues and Williams (2011) write, “because most universities now have student portal and use web-based learning management system as fundamental aspect of course delivery”. This definitely includes the use of social media platforms such as Facebook to engage students.

The following themes emerged from the narratives written by the students participants:

Theme 1: Accessibility on Facebook

As some students have stated, Facebook is an important tool for learning. Their responses demonstrates this: “ In terms of passing tasks like projects, Facebook has had a beneficial impact on my academic success in school. It is easier to upload than to give it straight to the teacher, than to burn it on a CD, and in a variety of other ways where there is already a much easier way to focus on”.(Respondent A) “All of the files we require have been sent, or will be sent, through the group page or group chat”.(Respondent B) The findings suggest that Facebook can be useful as a learning tool. The integration of Facebook as an educational project or route for project submission with pre-determined purposes and results for the learning experiences becomes more relevant and productive (Kbilan et al, 2010). However in order for teachers and students to get the most out of technology, it must be easily available.

Theme 2: In the process of learning, Facebook usage activates self- awareness : Not everything is nice all of the time; everything has its limitations. In this regard, Facebook can

be beneficial to people, particularly students, but it can be a source of distractions if not used responsibly. Students use Facebook to keep up with what's going on at school, but it may also be a source of temptation for them. They were enticed to scroll down and see some posts about their peers instead of studying. “ It has a beneficial influence on me at times, such as making me aware of what is going on at school or keeping me informed about developments in my studies. Facebook, on the other hand, ha somehow or most of the time become a source of distraction”.(Respondent C)

Students nowadays can enjoy a comfortable life while studying thanks to Facebook. However, in addition to the benefits it may provide, it may have a negative impact on pupils, particularly their academic performance. A large presence on Facebook and the resulting increased levels of information flow management can engage students in some tasks while they are constantly engaged in interaction and socialization, which disrupts their focus on their academic tasks. One of the respondents stated that her ability to concentrate on studying is hampered since her mind is occupied with Facebook. One of the respondents also stated that she spends her time scrolling on Facebook rather than studying her notes or working on her assignments or projects. Facebook addiction disorder had been studied by many psychologists (Brailovskaia, 2018).

Theme 3: The benefits and drawbacks of Facebook use in academic performance : These days, students are heavily influenced by the use of Facebook. It can be used for a variety of purpose, including communication, acquiring information, sharing diverse points of view and thought, and forming various relationships with strangers. This could explain why they continue to use Facebook and have made it a daily habit. Furthermore, Facebook can be considered one of the distractions that can cause students' attention to be diverted from their schoolwork. Furthermore, Facebook has little effects on college students' academic performance because it does not divert their attention away from their studies. In simple ways, as long as students use Facebook in moderation, there is no way that it will divert them from their academic achievement. “I didn't get any negative impact on my academic performance because I had to balance my studies and usage of Facebook. I never let Facebook empowered me. I use it in control manner”. (Respondents D)

Although Facebook is beneficial for students in terms of connectivity such as exchanging knowledge, socialization and other constructive activities. The literature shows that “Facebook has become dangerously addictive, disrupting students activities and academic goals on a regular basis” (Nadem et al, 2020). As a result, if students pay close attention to their academic business, Facebook will never be a hindrance to their academic accomplishment.

The Covid-19 pandemic ushered in a new era of instruction, particularly in higher education. Facebook is one of the learning tools used by teachers, according to the result of survey questionnaire distributed via Google Forms and completed by undergraduate students. This is extremely beneficial to learning, as internet connectivity is constantly a

concern. Furthermore, students describe Facebook as an alternate tool in teaching and learning based on their narratives.

Conclusion: Facebook is social networking platform that may be used for both amusement and education. The usage of Facebook as a tool in education, in teaching learning benefits students' social interaction as well as their academic achievement in school. Because of its accessibility, using Facebook as an instructional tool for sending notes and presentation during the Covid-19 pandemic, it has a good impact.

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